

TECHNOLOGIES FOR MANUFACTURING ROLLS FOR ROLLING MILLS WITH WEAR-RESISTANT POWDER-BASED WELD OVERLAY COATINGS AND THEIR HEAT TREATMENT

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Abstract. *It is also pertinent to highlight that the high level of new innovative technologies in foreign countries has predetermined a significant lag in the domestic industry manufacturing metal products for its own consumption, in connection with which a number of Uzbek metallurgical and machine-building plants are focused on the consumption of foreign analogues of metal products. This is mainly due to the low quality of cast parts of domestic enterprises, such as "non-liquid assets" of steel and cast iron products used for the mass production of metal products.*

Keywords: *cyclic exposure, foam models, molten coating, wear-resistant.*

Introduction

The main reason for the lack of competitiveness of domestic steel parts is their low operational durability on automated lines for the production of metal products due to the appearance of relief on the working surfaces (or edges) during their operation due to the burnout of the necessary inclusions and the formation of cracks in places of thermal shock [1]. One of the features of operation of these parts is cyclic exposure to high temperatures in an uninterrupted mode until the complete wear of the metal set forming the molten coating, due to which strict requirements are imposed on cast parts for thermal, heat, wear and corrosion resistance, thermal fatigue and mechanical processing conditions.

The aim of the work. The aim of this work is the technology of manufacturing cast machine parts with a hard-alloy wear-resistant coating by casting on lost foam models and increasing their hardness and wear resistance by the method of optimal double heat treatment.

Equally important is the fact that forming the required structure of the parts, both in the cast state and after their heat treatment, parts were selected that operate in contact with the molten coating at 900-11500C, manufactured in the foundry of the Metallmexqurilish Holding Company in sand molds by casting on lost foam models. Such parts include metallurgical steel rollers of a rolling mill with a wear-resistant powder-like surfacing coating with a layer thickness of 1.0 to 3.0 mm [2]. The chemical composition of steel 35GL is shown in Table 1, which is used to make the casting of the part.

This process is available in implementation, easily regulated, allows you to get models of a very simple and complex configuration with different wall thicknesses, significant overall dimensions, with a given density, accuracy and surface purity. After drying, the finished models were covered with a layer of non-stick paint (a mixture of asbestos powder with a binder) and after repeated drying, the foam models were fixed in the flask-container using the elements of the riser-

collectors and the gating system. After assembling the foam models, they were molded with dry quartz sand (1K0315, etc.) to the top of the flask and simultaneously compacted with pneumatic vibration.

Table 1

Chemical composition of steel 35GL

C	Si	Mn	Ni	Cr	Cu	As	P	S	Fe
0,32-0,4	0,17-0,37	0,5-0,8	To 0,25	To 0,25	To 0,25	To 0,08	To 0,035	To 0,04	~ 97

Moreover, all foam models are placed horizontally, and their working surface is upward (Fig. 1, a). To form a wear-resistant surfacing coating during the casting process, a paste was prepared consisting of powders of hard alloy PG-S27 and a solution of 4% polyvinyl butyral in alcohol (a certain percentage by weight). These pastes were applied to the working surface of the foam model (Fig. 1, b, c) and subjected to heat drying. After drying, the foam models were again fixed in the casting flask-container. Then the flask was installed in the main conveyor and filled with liquid metal at a temperature of 1539-16500C through the gating system with a siphon supply of metal. The molten metal was fed directly to the foam model. Under the action of this melt, the polystyrene gasifies and the forming cavity is filled with metal according to the composition corresponding to steel grade 35GL. In this regard, the chemical composition of the sormite type hard alloy of the PG-S27 brand is investigated in the work. The composition of the applied coating was selected based on two criteria: 1 - the coating should meet the requirement of a 3-5-fold increase in wear resistance compared to the wear resistance of the steel base; 2 - the coating should include available and inexpensive components and be distinguished by the simplicity of its application technology. Based on this, the sormite hard alloy was chosen. In this way, a casting of a part with a wear-resistant surfacing coating is obtained (Fig. 1, g).

Fig. 1. Foam model of a steel roller of rolling mill No. SP1413.16, manufactured by casting on gasifiable models with a wear-resistant surfacing coating: a-foam model of a roller; b, c-foam model of a roller with a coating over the entire wear surface coating; d-cast steel roller with a wear-resistant surfacing coating and after heat treatment.

Filling the mold with liquid metal is one of the main stages of forming a casting, determining many indicators of its quality. It should be noted that pouring of molds should be done especially carefully, accurately and uniformly at a constant hydrostatic pressure.

Research results and their discussion. To check the thickness of the casting layer, we took one of the finished steel parts with a hard-alloy wear-resistant coating [3], cut out a piece of the section for macro- and micro-examination, then ground and polished it, and then washed and etched with a special etchant to reveal a surface coating with a layer thickness of 2-3 mm (Fig. 2, a). The layer thickness is more clearly and visually represented on the macrostructure (Fig. 2, b).

Fig. 2. Structure of steel sample with hard alloy powder surfacing coating: a-etched sample with coating thickness of 2.5 mm; b-structure of surface coating with layer thickness of 3.0 mm. X500

Conclusion

It can therefore be deduced that obtained cast parts with wear-resistant surfacing coating were subjected to heat treatment (quenching + tempering) in different modes: quenching 900-11500C, tempering 300-6000C. After heat treatment of cast parts, hardness and wear resistance increase by 3-4 times compared to serial products [4]. This innovative technology has been implemented in JSC Uzmetkombinat with economic effect.

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